

HORIZON 2020

Research and Innovation action

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ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:

**A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic**

Deliverable 3.1

Webinar recording on Proposal Writing

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	Educating a new generation of polar researchers and professionals
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Abstract

In the frame of WP3 “Educating a new generation of polar researchers and professionals”, APECS held a webinar with the topic “Proposal Writing” on 25 April 2019.

Webinar on “Proposal Writing”

The webinar on „Proposal Writing“ was coordinated along the second „Call for ship-time“ of ARICE. The aim was to give potential applicants the opportunity to get hints and advices on how to write a successful proposal in general and learn about the application process in ARICE, as well as to facilitate questions and an active discussion.

Speakers

We invited speakers with great experience in research support and editing proposals of researchers and responsible project members of ARICE.

Imke Fries, research support officer at the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, has been supporting the drafting of numerous national and EU project proposals. Imke gave a general introduction to successful proposal writing including important steps to consider before starting the writing process, hints on the review process, time planning, typical proposal elements and the actual writing of a proposal.

Dr Verónica Willmott, ARICE project manager at AWI, and **Dr. Nicole Biebow**, ARICE project coordinator at AWI, talked about how to write a ship-time proposal, with a focus on the ARICE Call for ship-time proposals 2019 including the application process and preparation of a realistic work plan.

Participants

The number of 119 registered participants indicates the great interest in the webinar topic but also that the selected webinar time of 9 am GMT is difficult to meet for e.g. US participants. 37 participants joined the webinar, 22 of them based at European countries and 15 at non-European countries.

Nationalities of the participants attending the webinar.

Australia	2
Austria	2
Belgium	1
China	1
Czech Republic	1
Denmark	2
Finland	3
France	2
Germany	6
India	2
Japan	1
Netherlands	1

Norway	4
Poland	1
South Africa	1
Switzerland	2
United Kingdom	3
United Arab Emirate	2

Discussion and feedback

A lively question & answer session developed after each of the presentations. After Imke's general introduction to proposal writing, participants asked how much the 'collaboration' part weighs into the proposal and the review, and what is the best timing and approach to contact potential collaboration partners. Further, there were questions asked about guidelines for budget calculations, as it seems difficult to come up with 'typical' numbers, e.g. for other countries, as well a success rates of explorative vs. applied or experimental proposals.

After Verónica's presentation on ship-time proposals, an interesting discussion developed regarding the level of experience of the main applicants and whether early career researchers encouraged applying. Even though postdoc contracts are often only for 1-2 years and provide a limited planning safety, Verónica and Nicole stressed out that early career researcher's applications are especially welcomed.

Overall a very positive feedback was received at the end of the webinar as comments in the chat box proved (e.g. “*clap* *clap* *clap*” or “Thank you for a great webinar. It was easy to understand the technicality of research through this presentation. Many thanks!” or “Thank you both for these great presentations” or “Thanks! Very helpful!”

Link:

This webinar was the second out of a webinar series of four. A recording as well as the presented slides are freely available on the ARICE website:

<https://arice.eu/training/webinars/72-arice-webinar-proposal-writing>